

Coupling-induced tunability of characteristic frequency of artificial hair cells

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Abstract. Drawing inspiration from nature, we develop bio-inspired acoustic sensors with integrated signal processing capabilities to (i) close the performance gap between the human hearing and machine hearing and (ii) test models on biological hearing. Particularly important is thereby the combination of frequency decomposition with nonlinear (compressive) amplification of the sound signals. Here, the question arises, how the frequency resolution of 0.1-0.4%, the large gain and the coverage of the large frequency range of 20 Hz to 20 kHz can be obtained with a modest number of 3000 inner hair cells as transducers without missing tones. To solve this issue, it was hypothesized that the cochlea can be modelled as coupled critical oscillators.

We study experimentally and theoretically the effects of coupling critical oscillators using bio-inspired acoustic sensors, which are based-on microelectromechanical system (MEMS) resonators with a high-quality factor and a resonance frequency set by the geometry. Using electronic feedback, these resonators act like critical oscillators tuned near Andronov-Hopf bifurcation point. If output-signal coupling is added, three different bifurcation points are generated. Tuning the system close to one of these bifurcation points leads to a highly tunable behavior and sound pressure dependent sensitivity that is compressive in nature. In this case, the response frequency of the sensor system can be shifted by tuning the control parameter for bifurcation, allowing to cover larger bandwidths with one sensor pair while retaining high quality factors. Furthermore, tuning coupling and feedback strength, bandwidth and gain of each sensor can be adapted as needed. Since efferent feedback can tune the response of outer hair cells and thus inner hair cells/basilar membrane as well, the question arises if such tuning mechanisms can be observed in the mammalian cochlea as well.

INTRODUCTION

Processing of sound signals in the cochlea strongly supports our sound and speech perception capabilities, i.e. a frequency resolution of 0.1-0.4% over a frequency range of 20 Hz to 20 kHz, a dynamic range of 120 dB SPL and recognition of speech even in very noisy environments with less than -10 dB signal-to-noise ratio [1–3]. Three main functionalities of the cochlea are thought to enable these properties: tonotopic frequency decomposition of sound signals, compressive amplification of the sound signal and dynamic adaptation of both. Here, inner hair cells (IHC) are responsible for transduction and Basilar membrane (BM), together with sensory and neural tuning and phase coding, yields a frequency decomposition of sound signals by its position-dependent resonance properties. Thereby, the scaling of bandwidth of the cochlea frequency filters with centre frequency yields an equalization of the power distribution of natural sounds and speech, thus encoding these more efficiently than fourier transform based filter with constant bandwidth [4, 5]. The somatic motility of outer hair cells (OHC) provides a feedback to basilar membrane motion yielding a sharp tuning and is discussed as underlying non-linear amplification [6, 7]. Efferent nerve fibres have the tendency to hyperpolarize OHC [8], hence making the amplification of OHCs adaptive. Thus, adaptive bandwidth and gain seem to be very important for sound perception in various hearing conditions.

We study how these properties can be implemented into technological systems to improve machine hearing and hearing-assistive technologies. Since some of the above mentioned properties, particularly the nonlinear amplification, resemble properties of a critical oscillator tuned to a critical point of Hopf bifurcation [9–11], it is hypothesized that each point on cochlea can be modelled as a critically tuned oscillator with a gradual descend of resonance frequency from 20 kHz at apex to 20 Hz at base [12, 13]. Tuning close to a Hopf bifurcation yields a high-Q system, i.e. a tuned amplifier with small bandwidth and high gain [13]. In the cochlea the frequency coverage (20 Hz to 20 kHz) and frequency resolution (0.1-0.4%) is achieved by mere 2000-3000 IHCs (See Fig. 1A,1C). This brings forth an important research question: How can the frequency resolution and bandwidth coverage achieved with a relatively small number of critical oscillators? One discussed explanation to this question is the coupling of critical oscillators, see e.g. [14]. As was shown previously, an ensemble of critical oscillators can behave as a single Hopf oscillator

when strongly coupled [15]. Furthermore, coupling can increase sensitivity and gain [16], and frequency clustering can occur for an array of coupled oscillators [17].

In this research work, we show that coupling of (critical) resonators can yield not only an increase in gain but also by changing criticality and coupling strength a dynamical adaptation of centre frequency and bandwidth, two properties, which have a strong effect on sound analysis performance. Therefore, we apply a technological model system consisting of multiple micro-electro-mechanical system (MEMS)-based resonators as acoustic sensor along with electronic feedback to obtain nonlinear dynamics and to realize the output-signal coupling. Since multiple coupling mechanisms exist in the cochlea, e.g. by overlaying tectorial membrane and fluid environment (see e.g. [16, 18]), and amplification tuning is achieved by efferent feedback, tuning of sound sensing properties (IHCs) can be a possible candidate to address the problem of covering a large bandwidth while simultaneously achieving a sharp tuning and a high gain. The sensor system and results will be described in detail in the next sections.

FIGURE 1: A: The tonotopical characteristics of cochlea can be modelled by a filter bank or array of critical oscillators. C: Due to sharp tuning, detection of tones between centre frequencies of filters can be disturbed (blue shaded region). B: An array of MEMS resonators with varying length can be used for implementation of tonotopy in a technological system. D: Using coupling and feedback, the frequency response of the each resonator (black curve) can be tuned, namely gain, bandwidth and resonance frequency can be modified by changing feedback strength a_f and coupling strength C_f .

SENSOR SYSTEM

The MEMS-based sensor system consists of a mechanical resonator for frequency-selective transduction of sound signals to electrical signals and a feedback loop for tuning the dynamics of the mechanical resonator (Fig. 2) [19, 20]. The resonator is a silicon beam with integrated piezoresistive deflection sensing and integrated thermomechanical

actuation [21]. The length l of the silicon beam ranges from $750 \mu\text{m}$ - $1350 \mu\text{m}$, the width $w = 750 \mu\text{m}$ and its thickness varies between $1 - 10 \mu\text{m}$. The natural frequency of the silicon beam depends mainly on its geometric dimensions, i.e. $f \sim d/l^2$ [19]. These silicon beams intrinsically show a linear response to sound input and have high Q factors in the range of $40 - 60$. Combining these beams with a (self-)feedback enables to tune the resonator properties like gain and bandwidth and can yield a nonlinear response, as was recently shown in [19, 22, 23]. Therefore, the deflection of each resonator is converted into voltage signals by a piezoresistive Wheatstone bridge, marked with green in Fig. 2, which is then amplified and high-pass filtered to yield the sensing signal u_{sens} . The feedback signal $u_{act} = a_f u_{sens} + u_{DC}$, consisting of amplifying the sensing signal u_{sens} and adding a bias voltage u_{DC} , is used to drive the aluminium heater on top of the beam. The FPGA of STEMLAB 125-14 board is used to calculate feedback (14bit ADC/DAC with 125 MHz sample rate each). The nonlinear response is thereby the result of a Hopf bifurcation in system dynamics, occurring at a specific combination of a_f and u_{DC} [19]. Here, output-signal coupling is added to the feedback. To realize this, the voltage signal of one resonator is multiplied with coupling strength C_f and used to drive the actuator of the second resonator and vice-versa for the second resonator. The actuation equations for both the oscillators are given by :

$$\begin{aligned} u_{act}^{(1)}(t) &= a_{f1} u_{sens}^{(1)} + c_f u_{sens}^{(2)} + U_{DC}^{(1)} \\ u_{act}^{(2)}(t) &= a_{f2} u_{sens}^{(2)} + c_f u_{sens}^{(1)} + U_{DC}^{(2)} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The resulting sensor properties are presented in the next section.

FIGURE 2: Implemented system design. Two silicon beam with integrated deflection sensing (green) and bimorph actuation (red) are used as acoustic sensor system. Feedback and coupling mechanisms are implemented in an FPGA. Sound input is played by a loudspeaker controlled via a signal generator. Sensing signals are recorded in the STEMLab 125-14 board.

FREQUENCY RESPONSES FOR COUPLED MEMS RESONATORS

Depending on the values of the feedback strength a_f and the coupling strength C_f , two feedback scenarios are applied here: (i) for $a_f = 0$ and $C_f \neq 0$ only output-coupling is used, and (ii) for $a_f \neq 0$ and $C_f \neq 0$, a combination of self-feedback and output-signal coupling is used. Note that in both cases a Hopf bifurcation is observed, depending on the combination of feedback strength and coupling strength. Here, we use the index *crit* for the parameter, at the bifurcation point. Above the bifurcation point, the system exhibits autonomous oscillations and loses its sensitivity for sound input. Thus, the parameters are chosen such that the system is tuned below the bifurcation point. The response of the sensor system thereby not only depends on the feedback and coupling strength but also on the difference in resonance frequency of the two sensors. Thus, four different responses can be observed, shown in Fig. 3: (i) using only coupling for small frequency difference (Fig. 3 A) or large differences (Fig. 3 C) and (ii) adding weak feedback (Fig. 3 B) or strong feedback (Fig. 3 D) to the coupling of sensors with nearby frequencies. To measure these, a sine wave sound signal is given with a sweep of frequency from $3000 - 5500$ Hz and amplitude of 15 mV. The sensing signal is recorded and a Fourier analysis performed and smoothed using a moving average to obtain the frequency

FIGURE 3: Frequency response in dependence of frequency difference (A,C) and self-feedback (B,D) for two coupled resonators. A,C: For nearby frequencies alignment of resonance frequencies to a common centre frequency is observed (A), while for distant frequencies both resonators respond at the opposite resonance peak as well (C), generating correlations between frequency bands. B,D: If resonators with nearby frequencies are coupled, the alignment and number of resonance peaks as well as the bandwidth can be adjusted by changing the self-feedback (criticality). Strong coupling and weak feedback enhances the response at common centre frequency (B). Weak coupling and strong feedback increases bandwidth and improves response of the mid-range frequencies (D).

responses shown in Fig. 3. Here, the uncoupled case without feedback is always compared to the respective coupling case. In the case (i) of using only coupling, Figure 3A shows response of silicon beams with nearby frequencies 3.63 kHz and 3.79 kHz. The critical coupling bifurcation point for this pair of oscillator is $C_{critical} = 1.2$ and as coupling strength 85% of the critical coupling strength were applied. In the uncoupled case both the oscillators show response only at their respective resonance frequencies. When strongly coupled below the bifurcation point, their resonance frequencies align to one common centre frequency, as is quite typical for coupled oscillators. Besides this, the response at the centre frequency is increased by 12 dB combined with a decrease of bandwidth. In contrast to this, in the case of coupling MEMS resonators with distant frequencies (3.63 kHz and 4.38 kHz), as shown in Figure 3C close to the bifurcation point, i.e. $C_f = 3.3$ with $C_{crit} = 3.5$, both resonators show a strong response at their natural frequencies and that of their coupled counterparts. This effect might be interesting for higher processing, since it creates a relationship between frequency bands, i.e. exciting one frequency in the (MEMS) cochlea can excite other frequencies too, if there is a strong coupling between them. Such an association between frequencies can support sound analysis, e.g. by an increased sensitivity for certain expected tones, helping to detect them even if the signal-to-noise ratio is low. For example, the pitch of a sound can be recognised even when only the higher harmonics are played without the fundamental frequency. Such property of perception can be exploited by associativity using coupling of the harmonics in tonotopy. The transition between both regimes, i.e. alignment of frequencies or association of frequencies, occurs in experiments (with a limited set of resonators) for frequency differences in the range of

400 – 500 Hz. However, this number strongly depends on the actual design and the properties of the resonators like quality factor, transfer factors etc.

The second case, coupling in combination with feedback, is shown in Figure 3B and D. If the coupling is strong ($\approx 44\%$ of $C_{crit} = 0.5625$) and only weak feedback is added (here: $a_f \approx 25\%$ of a_{crit} without coupling) alignment of resonance peaks at one common center frequency, similarly to the case of only strong coupling. However, the addition of a weak feedback significantly enhances the response at the centre peak compared to the case without feedback. In contrast to this, if the feedback is strong ($a_f \approx 72\%$ of a_{crit}) and the coupling is weak ($\approx 21\%$ of C_{crit}), as shown in 3D, the systems behaves more like two resonators with large frequency difference, i.e. there are two peaks at the natural resonance frequency of both the resonators. Additionally the response in the mid range frequency is significantly enhanced, giving an enhanced overall bandwidth. Thus, adding feedback to the coupling allows to increase the gain and switch between alignment of frequencies and association of frequencies. How the sensing properties like bandwidth, frequency and gain depend on the feedback and coupling strength is demonstrated in the next section.

Tuning of sensor properties

FIGURE 4: Tuning of centre frequency (A) and bandwidth (B): two resonators with natural frequency $f_1 = 3630\text{Hz}$ and $f_2 = 3790\text{Hz}$ are coupled. A: resonance frequency of resonator 2 with natural frequency of $f_2 = 3790\text{Hz}$ in dependence of feedback strength, if the system is tuned to the bifurcation point by the combination of feedback and coupling. B: Bandwidth of resonator 2 in dependence of feedback and coupling strength. Bifurcation occurs for $C_{crit} = 1.03$ ($a_f = 0$) and for $a_{crit} = 0.375$ ($C = 0$).

The sensing properties of the two resonators strongly depend on the feedback and coupling strength. Thereby one can differentiate between properties at the bifurcation point or below the bifurcation point. At the bifurcation point, the quality factor is theoretically large, i.e. the bandwidth is very small, enabling a very sharp tuning with high frequency resolution. At or close to this point, for resonators with a small frequency difference, the common centre frequency of both can be tuned by varying the feedback strength (Fig. 4A) [24]. Here, two MEMS resonators with frequencies $f_1 = 3630\text{ Hz}$ and $f_2 = 3790\text{ Hz}$ are coupled. The feedback strength is varied in the range of $a_{f1}, a_{f2} \in [-0.5, 0.15]$ and for each set of feedback strengths the coupling strength is modified such that the system is close to the bifurcation point. Sound sweep is applied and frequency response is calculated from the recorded sensing signals. The frequency of the peak value s extracted as centre frequency. Fig. 4A shows the color coded centre frequency of resonator 2 ($f_2 = 3790\text{ Hz}$). By changing the feedback strength the centre frequency can be tuned in the range $[f_1, f_2]$. Thus, the whole range $[f_1, f_2]$ can be covered while keeping a sharp tuning of the response.

Tuning the system not so close to the bifurcation point, allows to modify not the frequency but rather the bandwidth of the sensor system. Fig. 4B shows the bandwidth of resonator 2 ($f_2 = 3790\text{ Hz}$) for different combinations of feedback strength and coupling strength, when coupled with resonator 1 ($f_1 = 3630\text{ Hz}$). Initially a bandwidth of

175 Hz is obtained. In general, if feedback strength or coupling strength are increased, i.e. the system is tuned closer to the bifurcation point, the bandwidth is decreased. However, for small feedback strengths and intermediate coupling strengths a relatively strong increase of bandwidth to 250 Hz occurs (e.g. $C \approx 0.4$ and $\mu \approx 0.3$). Bandwidth is important, when designing the array of resonators to cover a certain frequency range. Larger bandwidth allow for a smaller number of sensors, but decrease the frequency resolution. Smaller bandwidths increase the frequency resolution but take longer times to settle. The optimal bandwidth for sound analysis is depending on the input signal characteristics [4]. Cochlea inspired bandwidth scaling yields a more uniform distribution of energies along the frequency bands. However, for vocalizations higher frequencies are slightly overemphasized whereas for background, environmental sounds this is true for lower frequencies. An adaptive sensor system, tuning the bandwidth for the current sound input, could thus contribute to a improved sound analysis. Since efferent feedback in the cochlea tunes the feedback of OHCs to BM motion, such a dynamic bandwidth scaling might be present in the cochlea as well.

DISCUSSION

Here, we studied the effect of coupling on two bio-inspired sensors. Each of them can undergo a Hopf bifurcation if feedback is added. Similarly, a Hopf bifurcation can be induced by coupling the resonators. Depending on the combination of feedback and coupling, different responses and hence sensor properties can be achieved. Thereby, either the two resonators align their resonance frequencies or an association of resonance frequencies can be obtained. Both effects can be utilised to improve sound analysis. If resonators are coupled, whose natural frequencies differ not too strongly, it is possible to tune the resonance frequency and/or the bandwidth of the sensor system by (dynamically) changing the feedback strength and coupling strength. This effect can be used to cover wide frequency range of 20 Hz to 20 kHz with a limited number of MEMS resonators and to overcome fabrication tolerances influencing resonance frequency. Furthermore, adapting the filter properties to the input signal characteristics can improve sound analysis. Since tuning of the amplification and nonlinearity is possible in mammalian cochleas by efferent feedback acting on OHCs, dynamical tuning of frequency and bandwidth depending on the input signal might be present there as well. Potential candidates for coupling mechanisms are here the cochlear fluid, the tectorial membrane and a signal coupling by efferent nerve fibres. Studies of tonotopy and tuning curves for various input signal could be a route to test this hypothesis.

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QUESTIONS AND ANSWERS

[Online forum]

[Martin Toderi] This is very interesting, artificially recreating the Hopf can open a lot of new experimental possibilities. I wonder how hard would it be to escalate, I personally don't know how these MEMS are made. You show two MEMS but reference "3000 hair cells", what would be a reasonable number to cover 20Hz-20kHz? Thinking about modeling the cochlea, it would be exciting to look into the properties of a bigger system tweaking the parameters. For these devices what would account for the "efferent feedback" in the experimental array, Is it a property of the MEMS or a specific parameter? How would you model it?

[Kalpan Ved] These MEMS resonators are fundamentally silicon beams. They are fabricated using complex step by step process which involves etching, sputtering, lithography and doping techniques. The fabrication process is explained in detail in [25]. The reason why we show two beams is because we want to study the fundamental effect of coupling and project these effect on ensemble of beams. Based on the simulation, we have observed that 64 beams are sufficient for efficient speech recognition. To cover the auditory range, with high frequency resolution, several hundreds of sensors would be required, which can be easily fabricated. Using coupling and feedback, we can reduce the number of necessary sensors to cover the range due to discussed the tunability. The electronic feedback and coupling in our systems is inspired by the influence of outer hair cell motility and hair bundle motility. It allows to tune the sensor properties like gain, bandwidth and frequency. Incorporating efferent feedback would relate to changing the parameters of feedback and coupling. This was introduced to realize sensory adaptation e.g. in [26].

[Stefanie Gutschmidt] The proposed research is highly commendable. Research findings make a significant contribution to current efforts to improve hearing-related technology. The authors successfully (experimentally) demonstrate how tuning of properties such as dynamic range, bandwidth and frequency tuning could be implemented in future sensor technology. The manuscript is already presented in a publishable standard. Addressing the following questions would further improve the quality and potential impact of their work:

1. What are the natural frequencies of these MEMS structures? And how does the frequency sweeps between 3000 and 5500 Hz relate? Are the devices operated in/near resonance?
2. When talking about coupling of these two oscillators, the coupling refers to coupled feedback mechanism, not structural coupling. What can be assumed about the structural coupling between these oscillators? Are they decoupled or potentially have additional coupling properties?
3. When varying feedback and coupling strengths, can any dominating effects be observed/discussed such as e.g. " a_f " is predominantly impacting the quality factor while " C_f " is influencing e.g. the frequency shifts or similar?
4. Regarding the presentation of results (Figures 3 and 4), what are the settings of other parameters, e.g. bias voltage and acoustic input strength etc?

[Kalpan Ved] Thank you for the nice comments. The answer to the questions are mentioned in same sequence

1. Here presented oscillators lies in the range of 3kHz to 5 kHz, particularly, sensor with resonance frequencies of 3.63 kHz, 3.73 kHz, 3.79 kHz and 4.38 kHz were applied for this study. When they are subjected to sound sweep ranging from 3-5.5 kHz. The sensors will respond to all frequencies, but show the highest gain at their resonance frequency. Thus, these devices are operated at resonance or near resonance.
2. At the moment there is no structural coupling between the oscillators, since each of them is mounted separately.
3. Yes, the combination of these two effects yields the shape shifting of bandwidths. It yields bandwidth tuning. This totally depends on the relative strengths of the feedback parameter a_f and coupling parameter C_f . If $C_f \gg a_f$ then you mainly see frequency shift. If $a_f \gg C_f$ then you mainly see high Q factors. Balancing both in the right amount tunes the bandwidth.
4. For figure 3 and 4 the biasing voltage was -300mV and applied sound pressure level (SPL) was around 0.06-0.08 Pascal.

[Post-talk Q&A]

[Aleksandrs Zosuls] Are the two oscillators coupled acoustically? What's your input source?

[Kalpan Ved] Two oscillators are electronically coupled and acoustically excited. There is no direct acoustic coupling.

[Aleksandrs Zosuls] Are the oscillators approximately close to one another such that both the oscillators are electro-mechanically coupled?

[Kalpan Ved] At the moment, the oscillators are not close enough. Hence they are not mechanically coupled. However, in the future, when these resonators will be packed into closed space, this effect needs to be considered.

[Aleksandrs Zosuls] Is one of the resonators acting like an electronic tank where it is storing energy and reflecting it in the electrical domain to couple into the other one?

[Kalpan Ved] There is a transfer of energy between both the resonators. The energy obtained by one resonator through acoustic excitation is electronically transferred to the neighbouring resonator and vice versa. This process of transfer of energy occurs in real time and there is no storage or tanking of acoustic energy.

[Sarah Verhulst] How many sensors will you need to cover the acoustic bandwidth of 20Hz-20kHz and is there a limit of how close you can put them together? If these resonators start pushing and pulling to the neighbouring ones then the dynamics of the sensor can get chaotic.

[Kalpan Ved] When using a sensor array as pre-processor for speech recognition, roughly 64 sensors were sufficient to obtain a high recognition rate of 90 % for spoken digits. Beyond 64 resonators we did not observe any improvement in the recognition rate. Here, the data was sampled with 8 kHz. To cover the auditory range, probably more sensors would be required. However, since coupling and feedback can be used to modify bandwidth and resonance frequencies, the number of sensors necessary to cover the auditory range can be reduced. Decoupling the sensors acoustically requires gaps between them of roughly 50 μm to avoid thermoviscous effects. In this case, the sensors would be (approximately) decoupled, if they do not share a common mounting, as it is currently realized.

[Daibhid O Maoileidigh] Can you increase the bandwidth without decreasing the gain of the system?

[Kalpan Ved] In principle, increasing the gain reduces the bandwidth. However, in the system of two coupled sensors for some parameter combinations we observe an increase in bandwidth without a decrease in gain (e.g. yellow region in fig. 4b).